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Teaching interest in B. Ed trainees at the entering level with respect to gender and subject stream

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Abstract

Teacher constitutes the real dynamic force in the school and in the educational system. It is said that progress of the nation and of mankind depends substantially on the teacher in a system of education. Teachers have a key role in the improvement of education. The interest in teaching of prospective teacher's effects on their teaching efficiency. Hence, the present study is intended to identify interest of B.Ed, trainees towards teaching at the entering level of the B.Ed, course. Descriptive survey method was employed for the study. Random sampling technique was used for the selection of the sample. The tool used for the data collection was Kakkar's Interest in Teaching Scale designed and standardized by Kakkar. The statistical techniques used for the analysis of the data were mean, S.D and t-test. The major findings include that the overall interest in teaching of the B.Ed, at the entering level was average and there was no significant difference found in the teaching interest of trainees with respect to gender and stream.

Keywords: Teaching interest, B. Ed trainees, gender, subject stream

1. Introduction

Teacher constitutes the real dynamic force in the school and in the educational system. The energy and forceful personality of teacher has direct and indirect impact on the coming generations and it is teacher who broadens the outlook of the youth under his charge, thus surpassing the international and geographical barriers. It is said that progress of the nation and of mankind depends substantially on the teacher in a system of education. Teachers have a key role in the improvement of education. Therefore, it is important that their best efforts be devoted to it. Since there is so much flexibility in the work they are required to do, and the manner in which they can do it, the contribution they make to the field will depend on their involvement in their work and the satisfactions they derive from it.

There is no component of teacher education which enjoys more supports from the education community and which is evaluated so positively by beginning teachers as students teaching. A growing number of individuals inside and outside the profession are raising questions about the very nature of student teaching. The interest in teaching of prospective teacher's effects on their teaching efficiency. Hence, the present study is intended to identify interest of B.Ed trainees towards teaching. Teaching students is a daunting challenge for most teachers. In the present era of heightened technological development students look for meaning and significance in relation to their own lives in what they are taught and knowledge is at their fingertips and now the students are no longer dependent on teachers for content knowledge. A clever teacher will capitalize on this and personalize their efforts with regard to what is going on in the lives of their students at the moment. Students want to know about now and not what happened a hundred years ago in some remote part of the world. Unfortunately, it may take a lot of effort on the part of the teacher but keeping up to date with technology and the events that may interest students is vital to getting and holding their attention. A creative teacher may organize activities like sharing journal entries or writing newspaper articles for newspaper students have created themselves. This allows students to express themselves freely and talk endlessly about a topic they are interested in their own ideas.

Prior to learning students need to know why they are doing something, how it can help them and how it relates to their lives.

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Everyone prefers interesting lessons but it is impossible to make all lessons fun as some subject matter is just boring by nature. Students are aware of this and even though they are generally in favor of fun they realize that good learning takes an effort.

There is a need to check the interest in teaching as it may happen that many or almost all the trainees may be the ones who are devoid of the bent of mind or aptitude necessary for teaching.

Hence the imperative need to ensure that the trainees admitted are those who have some teaching aptitude or interest, as otherwise the training programme would neither be fruitful nor effective and economical, A number of factors necessary, for being successful in teaching, constitute as a whole the aptitude for teaching. Intellect, attitude towards children, interest in teaching, sincerity, self-acceptance, knowledge of subject matter, knowledge, of children, professional growth and personality may be some such factors, Though quite a few of these are important and are required to be assessed in the case of trainees seeking admission, interest in teaching seems to be a relatively more significant and essential factor.

2. Review of related literature

Jain (1982) [1] studied-Classroom Behavior Pattern of teachers in relation to their attitude towards profession, morale and values. and found that teachers with a high aesthetic value did not have a favorable attitude towards teaching profession and teachers and those with high religious value had favorable attitudes towards teaching profession, educational process and pupils and teachers.

More (1998) [2] examined-The Relationship Between Teaching Effectiveness, Teaching Aptitude and Personality Traits and found that personality was positively correlated with teaching effectiveness, of which intelligence was the most important. Teaching effectiveness and teaching ability have positive correlation and the total personality of the teacher is found to be including effective teaching and ineffective teaching.

Peterson (1972) [3] studied —Teacher Attitudes Towards Professionalism, Job Satisfaction and Collective Negotiations: A Cross Cultural-Study and found a positive relationship between attitudes of Washington teachers and most demographic characteristics i.e., age, sex, and amount of teaching experience.

2.1 Need and Significance of the study

The present study focuses on measuring the interest in teaching of the prospective teachers as it will provide

alertness and desirable behavior in the classroom and maintain cool personality traits, positive attitude, which are helping in enhancing the teacher’s effectiveness. Teachers have a key role in the improvement of education. Therefore, it is important that their best efforts be devoted to it. Since there is so much flexibility in the working patterns and teaching style so they are required to do, and the manner in which they can do it, the contribution they make to the field will depend in part on their involvement in their work and the satisfactions they derive from it.

2.2 Objectives of the Study

1. To study the teaching interest of B.Ed. trainees at the entering level.
2. To study the teaching interest of B.Ed. trainees in relation to their gender.
3. To study the teaching interest of B.Ed, trainees in relation to their subject stream

2.3 Hypotheses

1. The teaching interest in B. Ed. trainees of Aurangabad city at the entering level is low.
2. There is no significant difference between the teaching in terest of B. Ed. trainees on the basis of their gender.
3. There is no significant difference between the teaching interests of B.Ed. trainees on the basis of their subject streams.

3. Methodology

Descriptive survey method was used in the present study.

3.1 Participants

For the selection of sample, stratified disproportionate random sampling technique was adopted. The sample consisted of 100 first year B. Ed college students comprising 50 males and 50 females from science and arts faculty.

3.2 Tools used

The tool used for data collection was Kakkar’s Interest in Teaching Scale designed and standardized by Kakkar, It consisted of 27 statements with five alternatives.

3.3 Statistics used

Mean, standard deviation and t- ratio were used to analyze the data.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1: Table showing mean scores of B.Ed trainees in interest in Teaching

Aspect	Obtained mean	Range of scores	Interpretation
Overall Teaching Interest.	10.850	Scores: 10 -18	Moderate Teaching Interest
Teaching interest of male trainees.	11.34	Scores: 10 -18	Moderate Teaching Interest
Teaching interest of female trainees.	10.36	Scores: 10 -18	Moderate Teaching Interest
Teaching interest of trainees from arts faculty.	9.26	Scores: 0 -9	Low Teaching Interest
Teaching interest of trainees from science faculty.	12.44	Scores: 10 -18	Moderate Teaching Interest

Table 2: Table showing the comparison of B. Ed Trainees with respect to gender and subject stream

Aspects/Scores	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-ratio
Gender	Males	11.34	1.341
	Females	10.36	
Subject Stream	Arts	9.26	4.790
	Science	12.44	

4.1 Major Findings and Discussions

1. From the mean value obtained in the above table no.1 we can interpret that the overall interest in teaching of the B.Ed. trainees of Aurangabad city at the entering level is 10.850 which shows Moderate interest in teaching.
2. From the mean value obtained in the above table no.2, we can interpret that the interest in teaching of the male B.Ed. trainees of Aurangabad city at the entering level is 10.36 which shows Moderate interest in teaching.
3. From the mean value obtained in the above table no.2, we can interpret that the interest in teaching of the female B.Ed. trainees of Aurangabad city at the entering level is 11.34 which shows Moderate interest in teaching.
4. From the mean value obtained in the above table no.2, we can interpret that the interest in teaching of the B.Ed. trainees of Aurangabad city belonging to arts faculty is 9.26 which shows Low interest in teaching.
5. From the mean value obtained in the above table no.2, we can interpret that the interest in teaching of the B.Ed. trainees of Aurangabad city belonging to science faculty is 12.44 which shows Moderate interest in teaching.
6. From the Table no.2, we can interpret that there is no significant difference in the teaching interest of the B.Ed. trainees with respect to gender as the obtained t-value is 1.341 which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance.
7. From the Table no.2, we can interpret that there is a significant difference in the teaching interest of the B.Ed. trainees with respect to their subject stream as the obtained t-value is 4.790 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. It can also be interpreted as trainees belonging to science faculty in Aurangabad city have more interest in teaching.

5. Conclusion

Teacher education is the foundation stone of nation's intellectual power which shapes the power profile of the nation in the community of the world nations, thus, it is rightly said that progress of a country particularly of a democratic country depends upon the quality to its teachers and for this reason teaching is the noblest profession among all the profession. Doga (2010) ^[6] emphasized on the fact that in a changing scenario one has to acquaint himself with life knowledge required for himself and his associates. All the formal and informal activities and experiences that help to qualify a person to shoulders the responsibilities as a member of the educational profession or to discharge his responsibilities more effectively. Patil (2010) ^[7] stated that quality of education primarily depends on the efficiency and effectiveness of teaching-learning process. Kothari Commission (1964-66) begins its report with the remarks that the destiny of India is being shaped in its classrooms. Hence, in order to improve the quality of education it is necessary to have a sound programme of teacher education irrespective of levels and types of education.

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